

Petrological Studies of Igneous Rocks Exposed in the Ka Dai Dutt Area, Kyaikhto Township, Mon State

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Abstract

The research area located in the western part of Kyaikhtiyo area, Kyaikhto Township, Mon State. It lies between Latitude 17° 25' to 17° 30' N and Longitude 96° 59' to 97° 4' E in one inch topographic map index of 94 C/15 and 94 G/3. The igneous rocks in the area consist of alkali feldspar granite, biotite granite, slightly foliated biotite granite and porphyritic biotite granite. Alkali feldspar, quartz, plagioclase and biotite are chief components and muscovite, chlorite and sericite are accessory minerals. These granitic rocks are regarded as S-type according to the mineralogical and petrological criteria. Field and petrological evidences indicate that the igneous rocks may be emplaced in Upper Mesozoic. The age is considered as Early Oligocene.

Introduction

Location

The study area is located in the western part of Kyaikhtiyo area, Kyaikhto Township, Mon State. It lies between Latitude 17° 25' to 17° 30' N and Longitude 96° 59' to 97° 4' E and in one inch Topographic Map index of 94 C/15 and 94 G/3 of Myanmar Survey Department. Location map of the study area is shown in (Fig.1).

Purpose

-To study the petrography and petrogenesis of the igneous rocks in the area.

Methods of Study

Field and Laboratory Work

1. Rock samples were acquired at all points where they change in characters.
2. For detailed microscopic study, about 15 thin sections.
3. These igneous rocks are analysed by using the mechanical point counter with the petrological polarizing microscope.
4. The plagioclase composition was interpreted by Michel-lévy method.

Fig.1 Location Map of the Study area

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Petrography

General Statement

The igneous rocks in the study area consist of alkalifeldspar granite, biotite granite, slightly foliated biotite granite and porphyritic biotite granite. These units are well exposed in the eastern part of the area. Nomenclature and classification of granitic rocks are based on the I.U.G.S classification (1989) as shown in (Fig.2).

Alkalifeldspar granite

Field and megascopic studies

It is well exposed along the Kadaidutt chaung and in the eastern part of Kadaidutt village. It is hard and compact. Exfoliation nature is presented (Fig.3). It is coarse-grained and microgranite dyke cross-cutting into the body of this rock unit. It is light grey colour on fresh surface.

Microscopic studies

It is typically coarse-grained and hypidiomorphic-granular texture. It consists of alkalifeldspar, quartz, plagioclase, biotite are essential minerals. The accessory minerals are muscovite, sericite and iron ore. Orthoclases occur as anhedral forms and cloudy appearance. Microclines are subhedral forms and show cross-hatched twinning (Fig.4). Perthitic and string perthitic nature are occurred. Plagioclase shows subhedral prismatic crystals and polysynthetic twinning. In some section, plagioclase feldspars are altered to sericite. According to the Michel-Lévy method, the compositional range of this unit falls within Ab90 – An 10 (Albite). Quartz grains are mostly anhedral crystals and wavy extinction due to strain effect. Biotite occurs as minor amount and shows subhedral prismatic form. Due to strain effect, biotite flakes are bent and twisted.

Biotite granite

Field and megascopic studies

Biotite granite is widely distributed along the stream sections, Meyongyi chaung, mountain peak (145meters) and eastern part of the study area. It is hard, compact, and moderately jointed. Sometimes, spheroidal weathering is occurred (Fig.5). It is coarse-grained and light grey colour on fresh surface.

Microscopic studies

It is coarse-grained, hypidiomorphic-granular texture. The essential minerals are alkalifeldspar, quartz, plagioclase and biotite. The accessory minerals are muscovite and iron ore. Orthoclase exhibits anhedral to subhedral forms and simple twinning (Fig.6). Microcline is subhedral form and shows cross-hatched twinning and perthitic texture (mostly string perthite) (Fig.7). Quartz grains show wavy extinction due to strain effect. Sometimes, mortar structure is observed in quartz. Plagioclases are observed as subhedral prismatic crystals. The compositional range of plagioclase is determined by Michel-Lévy method falls within Ab70 – An30 (Oligoclase). Biotite is subhedral form. In some sections, it altered to chlorite (Fig.8).

Slightly foliated biotite granite

Field and megascopic studies

It is occurred in the northwestern part of Saungnaing village. Megascopically, it is coarse-grained and slightly foliated biotite minerals are observed on the surface (Fig.9). It is mainly composed of quartz, feldspar and biotite. The fresh colour is grey and weather is dark grey.

Microscopic studies

It is coarse-grained, hypidiomorphic-granular texture. The constituent minerals are alkalifeldspar, quartz, plagioclase, biotite, muscovite and iron ore. Alkalifeldspars are orthoclase and microcline. Orthoclases are subhedral to anhedral crystals. Sometimes, zoning of orthoclase is observed (Fig.10). Microclines are subhedral and cross-hatched twinning. String perthite is also occurred in some places. Quartz occurs as anhedral crystal. It shows suture contact and undulatory extinction (Fig 11&12). The compositional range of plagioclase is Ab90-An 10 (Albite) by Michel-Lévy method. Biotite is subhedral prismatic crystal. Some are altered to chlorite. Muscovite is found as minor amount.

Porphyritic biotite granite

Field and megascopic studies

It is mainly exposed along the stream sections, peak of Lerpatu taung, Saungnaing chaung and northeastern part of the study area (Fig.13). This unit is hard and compact, and spheroidal weathering is occurred. It is coarse-grained and porphyritic nature is observed. Feldspar phenocrysts are randomly oriented and sizes of feldspar phenocrysts are 0.02 m to 0.08 m in length (Fig 14). It is dark grey colour on weather surface.

Microscopic studies

It is coarse-grained, porphyritic and hypidiomorphic-granular texture. The essential minerals are alkalifeldspar, quartz, plagioclase, muscovite and biotite. Orthoclase shows anhedral to subhedral prismatic form and simple twinning nature. Microcline and perthite (mostly string perthites) are observed. Quartz grains are anhedral crystals and mortar structure of quartz grain is observed (Fig 15). Plagioclase is occurred as minor constituent and subhedral form. Myrmekitic texture is also occurred (Fig 16). The compositional range confirmed by Michel-Lévy method falls within Ab90-An10 (Albite).

Fig.2 Plotted data of the igneous rocks on the I.U.G.S classification diagram (1989).

Fig.3 Spheroidal weathering feature of alkalifeldspar granite at Kadaidutt chaung (Loc. G563195)

Fig.4 Cross-hatched twinning of microcline in alkalifeldspar granite

Fig.5 Exfoliation feature of biotite granite at Meyongyi chaung (Loc.G556177).

Fig.6 Simple twinning of orthoclase in biotite granite.

Fig.7 String perthite in biotite granite.

Fig.8 Biotite altered to chlorite in biotite granite.

Fig.9 Alignment of biotite minerals in slightly foliated biotite granite in northwestern part of Saungnaing village Loc.G557145).

Fig.10 Zoning of orthoclase in slightly foliated biotite granite.

Fig.11 Muscovite mineral and wavy extinction of quartz in slightly foliated biotite granite.

Fig.12 Subhedral orthoclase and mortar structure of quartz grain in slightly foliated biotite granite.

Fig.13 Nature of porphyritic biotite granite at Lerpatu taung (Loc.G579177)

Fig.14 Randomly oriented nature of feldspar phenocrysts in porphyritic biotite granite at Saungnaing chaung (Loc.G565136).

Fig.15 Mortar structure of quartz in porphyritic biotite granite.

Fig.16 Myrmekitic texture in porphyritic biotite granite.

Petrogenesis

Origin of Granitic Rocks

Granitic rocks of the area are considered to be magmatic origin according to the following aspects:

1. Presence of twinning and zoning of feldspar.
2. Presence of biotite mica in granitic rocks.
3. Presence of perthites (mostly string perthites) and alkalifeldspar phenocrysts.
4. Presence of myrmekitic texture in granitic rocks.

Types of Granitic Rocks

The granitic rocks of the area are considered as S-type. It is supported by the following evidences:

1. Presence of muscovite in granitic rocks units.
2. Biotite is presented as principal mafic mineral.
3. Hornblende is absent within the granitic rocks.

Emplacement of Granitic Rocks

The igneous rocks of the area are considered to have emplaced in the Upper Mesozoic. The evidences are as follows:

1. Regional metamorphism of greenschist facies is presented and contact metamorphic aureoles are present.
2. Contact migmatites are absent.
3. Dykes and veins are common in granitic rock.
4. Metasedimentary enclaves are absent in granitic body.

Mechanism of Emplacement

These granitic intrusions were emplacement during syn-tectonic, based on the following evidences:

1. Alignments of biotite minerals in slightly foliated biotite granite are occurred.
2. Wavy extinction is found in quartz grains.
3. Presence of bending of cleavages in biotite flakes.
4. Breaking of twin bands in plagioclase feldspars.

Possible Age of Granitic Rocks

The possible age of granitic rocks in the area is based on the radiometric dating of the granite samples which were collected by the G.I.A.C Field Trip (1996) is as following;

Kyaikhto Area	Porphyritic Granite (K-Ar method)	my. 96.211 Bio. 31.09±Ma
Kyaikhto Area	Isotropic Granite (K-Ar method)	my. 96.213 Bio. 32.2 Ma

Therefore, possible age of the igneous rocks of the area was probably during Early Oligocene age (32.2 Ma and 31.09 Ma).

Result and Discussion

The igneous rocks in the resesarch area are consists of alkalifeldspar granite, biotite granite, slightly foliated biotite granite and porphyritic biotite granite. Nomenclature and classification of granitic rocks are based on the I.U.G.S classification (1989). Granitic rocks of the present research area are considered to magmatic origin and S-type. They are considered to have emplaced in the Upper Mesozone and Early Oligocene age (32.2 Ma and 31.09 Ma).

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my thank to Dr. Aye Aye Tun, Rector and Dr. Yin Yin Than, Pro-Rector, Bago University, for their permission to present this paper and valuable advice.

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